

ANALYSIS OF UZBEK ATHLETES WHO HAVE ACHIEVED PRESTIGIOUS RESULTS IN FIGURE SKATING

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FIGURALI UCHISH SPORT TURIDAN NUFUZLI NATIJALARNI QAYT ETGAN O'ZBEKISTON SPORTCHILARNING TAHLILI

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Annotation: In this article, the major achievements and lower results in the sports careers of Misha Ge and Ilia Malinin are analyzed.

Key words: Misha Ge, Ilia Malinin, Uzbekistan Championship, Skate Canada, Winter Olympic Games, figure skating, sports achievements.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Misha Ge va Ilia Malinning sport faoliyatidagi eng yirik yutuqlari va past ko'rsatkichlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Misha Ge, Ilia Malinin, O'zbekiston chempionati, Skate Canada, Qishki Olimpiya o'yinlari, figurali uchish, sport yutuqlari.

Topic relevance: Ilia Malinin was born on December 2, 2003, in Arlington, Virginia. Malinin's acquaintance with ice skating began in childhood. He took an interest in sports from a young age, making his first steps on local ice grounds. Her father, in turn, was a person interested in music, which was a source of inspiration for Ilia. Ilia strove to achieve success through her many training sessions with her father's motivation and support.

He suffered a major injury when he was very young, which hampered his career. But these difficulties made him stronger. He continued to prepare constantly to recover his health and prove himself once again. Malinin's flying style represents a blend between technical skills and the expression of creativity. It combines a complex jumping sequence with modern step movements and emotional choreography, providing the viewer with an engaging stage presentation. Personal life Malinin draws attention not only to her sporting career, but also to her personal life. He also dedicates time to his hobbies, such as listening to music and learning according to his interests. Spending time with family and friends motivates and reduces stress. He attributes his success in the sport to his family and coaches, who constantly support him.

Misha Ge, full name Misha Aloyzievich Ge, was born on 17 May 1991 in Moscow, Russia. His parents are figure skating coaches, and Misha started skating at an early age due to his interest in the sport. Starting at the age of 4, Misha began learning ice skating, which allowed her to perfectly combine dance and technique at the same time. Members of the family, particularly his mother,

Larisa Ge, spent time with him, conducting programs and exercises aimed at creating perfect figures.

In 2009, Misha joined the national team of Uzbekistan and had the opportunity to showcase his high talent on the international stage. In the competitions he participated in, he always strived to further improve his technical skills and artistic expression. With each performance, Misha established high standards in Uzbekistan figure skating.

The 2014 Winter Olympics in Sochi, Russia, became an important turning point for Misha Ge. He represented Uzbekistan and demonstrated his creative skills. His performances in Sochi impressed audiences not only technically but also artistically. In 2018, Misha Ge decided to end his athletic career, but he did not move away from the ice. Today, she is coaching and choreographing, sharing her knowledge, experience, and creative approach with young figure skaters.

Misha's coaching style has many facets, he teaches young athletes not only the technique of figure skating, but also the expression of feelings on the stage. It inspires students to freely express themselves on stage, understand the music, and add their emotions to the dance. His coaching activities are important in preparing young athletes for the team and the stage.

Misha Ge is also an interesting and comprehensively developed personality in his personal life. He is interested in the art and music he loves and strives to correctly understand artistic images in his creative processes. In addition to sports, Misha loves music and literature, which also has a positive impact on his creative processes.

Table -1

An analysis of Ilia Malin's achievements in figure skating.

Seasonal competition titles	2020–21	2021–22	2022–23	2023–24	2024–25
World Championships		9 st Place	3 st Place	1 st Place	TBD
Grand Prix Final			3 st Place	1 st Place	TBD
USE Championships		2 st Place	1 st Place	1 st Place	
World Team Cup			1- o'rin (2 st Place)		
Finland Grand Prix			1 st Place		
France Grand Prix				2 st Place	
American Grand Prix	5 st Place		1 st Place	1 st Place	1 st Place
Canadian Grand Prix					1 st Place
Autumn Classic Series				1 st Place	
Austrian Cup			3 st Place		
Lombardia Cup					1 st Place
U.S. E Classic Series			1 st Place		
Challenge Cup			1 st Place		
Japanese Open championship		2- st Place (2- st Place)	2- st Place (1- st Place)		

Comment: The analysis of Ilia Malinin as an athlete with the highest results among Uzbek figure skaters.

Table -2

An analysis of Ilia Malinin's achievements in figure skating during her athletic career

Seasonal competition titles	2009-2010	2010-2011	2011-2012	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018
Winter Olympic Games					17				17
World Championships		30	19	16	27	6	15	12	9
Four Continents Championships		12	9	11	13	8		9	6
Grand Prix Chinese Cup						5	8		
Grand Prix: Rostelecom Cup					8	4			4
Grand-pri Skate Canada								6	
Grand-pri: Trophée de France								7	3
Uzbekistan Championships	1	1					1	1	
Asian Winter Games		6						6	
Asian Trophy		2		2					
Finland Trophy				6		4			
Warsaw CUP				2					
Autumn Classic International competition								2	4
NRW Trophy				5					
Nitce International Cup			8						
Ice challenge			2	4					
Denkov-Stavisky Cup				1	1		1		

Comment: Misha Ge's analysis as an athlete with the highest results among Uzbek figure skaters.

Ikkinchi jadvalda berilgan berilgan ma'lumotlar Ilia Malinin tomonidan yuqori nomdor musobaqalarda qatnashishi hamda erishgan natijalarining umumiy xisobi bo'yicha raqamlarda qayd etilgan. Bundan tashqari qatnashish jarayonida har yillik natijalarning o'sishi yoki yomonlashishini ham aniqlash mumkin.

Table -3

An analysis of Ilia Malinin's achievements in figure skating during her athletic career

COMPETITION PARTICIPATION	Competitions	Ilia Malinin	Year	Competitions	Misha GE	Year
	Winter Olympic Games	4 st Place	2022	Winter Olympic Games	17 st Place	2013-2014
	World Championships	2 st Place	2023	World Championships	6 st Place	2014-2015
	Four Continents Championships	3 st Place	2023	Four Continents Championships	6 st Place	2017-2018
	Grand Prix Stages			Grand Prix: Chinese Cup	5 st Place	2014-2015
	Cup of China	1st Place	2023	Grand Prix: Rostelecom Cup	4 st Place	2014-2015
	Rostelecom Cup	1st Place	2022	Grand-pri: Skate Canada	6 st Place	2016-2017
	Skate Canada	1st Place	2022	Grand-pri:Trophée de France	3 st Place	2017-2018
	Trophée de France	1st Place	2022	Uzbek championships	1st Place	2009-2010
	Uzbek championships	1st Place	2023	Asian Winter Games	6 st Place	2010-2011
	Asian Winter Games	1st Place	2023	Asian Trophy	2 st Place	2010-2011
	Asian Trophy	1st Place	2023	Finlandiya trofeyi	4 st Place	2014-2015
	Finland Trophy	2 st Place	2022	Warsaw Cup	2 st Place	2012-2013
	Warsaw Cup	1st Place	2023	International Autumn Classic competition	2 st Place	2016-2017
	International Autumn Classic competition	1st Place	2023	NRW Trophy	5 st Place	2012-2013
	NRW Trophy	1st Place	2023	Nitce International Cup	8 st Place	2011-2012
	Nitce International Cup	1st Place	2023	Ice challenge	2 st Place	2011-2012

Comment: Comparison of the overall results of two major Uzbek athletes with the highest sporting results.

A generalized form of all the major achievements of Ilia Malinin and Misha Ge in the sport of figure skating during their sports career. Misha Ge won his biggest achievement at the Uzbekistan Championships in 2010 and took 1st place. His lowest score was at the 2014 Winter Olympics, where he placed 17th. Ilia Malinin won her biggest achievement at Skate Canada in 2022, finishing 1st. His lowest score was in 2022 when he took 4th place at the Winter Olympics.

In conclusion, it can be noted that when comparing Misha Ge and Ilia Malinin in terms of success and low performance in figure skating, the achievements of both athletes are unique and impressive, and their contributions to the sport of figure skating are of great importance. Misha Ge has represented Uzbekistan in a number of international competitions and was the 1st runner-up at the 2010 Uzbekistan Championships. However, her 17th-place finish at the Sochi 2014 Olympic Games is remembered as her lowest performance. Ilia Malinin, who

is one of the athletes shaping the future of figure skating with her creative and technical approach, finished 1st at the 2022 Skate Canada. Malinin's lowest score is 4th place at the 2022 Winter Olympics. Both athletes' unique abilities, strong mental state, and dedication to the sport led them to take their place in the world of figural flying. Their achievements are widely recognized on a global sporting scale, increasing the likelihood of achieving even greater success in the future.

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